

Kinetics of ion diffusion in Lewatit in aqueous isopropanol media

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Manuscript received 26 March 2001, revised 20 November 2001, accepted 1 March 2002

The kinetics of ion exchange reaction between $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{H}^+$ mixed solvent (water-isopropanol) media on Lewatit (cation exchanger) using batch technique have been investigated in the temperature range 20–52°. The effects of isopropanol concentration, particle size of the sorbent material and temperature on the sorption rate have been reported. The slowest step governing the sorption has been found to be diffusion within the exchanger particles for the mixed solvent systems. The effective diffusion coefficients have been evaluated at three different temperatures. The energy barriers against the diffusion of exchanging ions have been estimated from the Arrhenius equation. Entropies of activation for the sorption processes have also been calculated.

Tsuk and Gregor¹ prepared a new class of non-aqueous swelling ion-exchange resins. Since then several publications appeared on theoretical and experimental developments in relation to the ion exchange behavior in mixed and pure non-aqueous media. The kinetic study of an oleophilic cation exchange resin of Gregor type of low capacity was carried out in absolute ethanol².

The exchange mechanism of Cs^+ (Cs^+-K^+ in aqueous medium) in simulated high-level liquid waste on potassium titanium hexacyanoferrate has been described³. The kinetics of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} uptake onto chelating resins (recovery from water) were modeled on the basis of the internal concentration profiles inside the exchanger bead⁴. Kinetic measurements were made on the extraction of divalent metal ions (Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} and Cd^{II}) with impregnated resin⁵. This process is accompanied by fast chemical reaction, characterized by a sharp moving boundary between the reacted shell and shrinking unreacted core within the impregnated resin. Analysis of the data of resorption rate showed to be in accordance with models used to explain the metal extraction. Kinetic measurements showed that the process is controlled by the rate of diffusion of the ions penetrating the reacted layer at high metal ion concentration (1×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}), and controlled by the rate of diffusion of the ions across the liquid film surrounding the resin particle at low metal ion concentration (1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}). Particle diffusion coefficients and mass transfer constants across the liquid film were determined from the graphical representation of the proposed models.

The present report concerns the kinetic studies of Fe^{III} ($\text{Fe}^{III}-\text{H}^+$) on Lewatit (H^+ -form) with an aim to obtain information about the mechanism of diffusion of this ion using different proportions of isopropanol and water mixed solvent systems.

Results and Discussion

Rate expression and evaluation of kinetic and thermodynamic parameters : The extent of exchange, F at time t has been determined as

$$F = \frac{\text{Amount of exchange sorption at time } t}{\text{Amount of exchange sorption at infinite time or at equilibrium}}$$

The equations 5 developed by Boyd *et al.*⁶ and later improved by Reichenberg⁷ have been applied for particle-diffusion-controlled rate processes. According to the expressions, if the rate of exchange sorption is governed by particle diffusion, i.e. the diffusion of exchanging ions through the exchanger is slowest, F is related to t and the particle radius r as

$$F = 1 - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-n^2 Bt)}{n^2}$$

where n is the number of exchanger particles and B the time coordinate. B is expressed as

$$B = \frac{\pi^2}{r^2} D_i$$

where D_i is the effective diffusion coefficient of ingoing ions, and r the radius of the particles. Plots of Bt vs t must be straight-lines passing through the origin. In the present studies, for every observed value of F , the corresponding Bt value has been obtained from Reichenberg's table⁷.

The energy of activation (E_a) associated with the sorption process has been determined by applying the Arrhenius type expression,

$$D_i = D_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right)$$

The pre-exponential constant D_0 gives the entropy activation (ΔS^*) as

Table 1. Effective diffusion coefficients (D_i) and thermodynamic parameters for the exchange sorption of ferric ion at different temperatures

Isopropanol % (v/v)	Radius of particle cm	$10^{-4} \times B$ s^{-1}			$10^{-6} \times D_i$ $cm^2 s^{-1}$			E_a kcal mol $^{-1}$	$10^{-7} \times D_0$ cm $^2 s^{-1}$	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal K $^{-1} mol^{-1}$
		20 $^\circ$	37 $^\circ$	52 $^\circ$	20 $^\circ$	37 $^\circ$	52 $^\circ$			
0.0	0.1	4.17	6.42	11.3	1.42	2.20	3.38	5.42	8.32	21.49
	0.2	3.50	5.42	8.33	0.51	0.79	1.38	6.21	2.77	23.68
30	0.1	2.33	3.67	7.50	0.78	1.25	2.50	6.62	3.74	23.08
	0.2	1.92	3.08	6.17	0.29	0.45	0.92	8.10	1.68	24.67
60	0.1	1.83	2.42	5.00	0.58	0.78	1.79	7.15	2.05	24.28
	0.2	1.42	1.92	4.42	0.23	0.30	0.61	9.11	1.13	25.46
90	0.1	0.58	1.42	2.50	0.17	0.37	0.80	8.00	0.83	26.07
	0.2	0.42	0.92	2.00	0.07	0.17	0.31	9.46	0.41	27.48

$$D_0 = 2.72 d^2 \frac{kT}{h} \exp^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R}$$

where k , h , and R are the Boltzmann, Planck and gas constants, respectively, d is the average distance between the successive exchange sites and is taken as 5 Å and T the temperature (K). All plots are drawn following to the method of least-squares. Standard deviations of the reported values are approximately 5%.

The effects of isopropanol concentration and temperature on the rate of exchange sorption are depicted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The $\log(1 - F)$ vs t plots (Mckay plots) are shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the logarithm of the effective diffusion coefficient ($\log D_i$)

Fig. 1. Rate of exchange at different isopropanol concentrations : (•) 0.0, (×) 30, (·) 60, (O) 90%.

and the reciprocal temperature (K^{-1}) for the sorption of ferric ions on the cation exchange resin. Table 1 records the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters associated with the present studies. The rate of exchange can be determined by three different steps : (a) particle diffusion, (b) liquid film diffusion and (c) mass action.

The nonlinear behavior of $\log(1 - F)$ vs time plots (Fig. 3) indicates that the rate is governed neither by film dif-

Fig. 2. Rate of exchange at different temperatures : (•) 20 $^\circ$, (×) 37 $^\circ$, (O) 52 $^\circ$.

Fig. 3. McKay plots of $\log(1 - F)$ vs t as a function of temperature : (×) 20 $^\circ$, (·) 37 $^\circ$, (•) 52 $^\circ$.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\ln D_i$ vs $1/T$ (K) : (•) 0.0, (—) 30, (×) 60, (O) 90%.

fusion nor by a mass action mechanism⁸. The shapes of these plots, called McKay plots⁹, are similar to those obtained for independent radioactive decay. The curves can be resolved into two linear components¹⁰ indicating the presence of two interdiffusion processes which comprise the overall rate of exchange, faster one corresponding to the residual curve and the slower one to the later linear portion of the McKay plot. This is further confirmed by the shape of F vs t plots (Fig. 1), which indicates that rapid initial uptake is followed by slower uptake of the effective ions. This suggests that the effective diffusion coefficients may be attributed to the simultaneous diffusion of the counterions through the pores of different size and electric fields. It is also clear from the residual curves that with the rise in temperature the contribution of the faster component of the effective diffusion is increased. These observations are similar to those of Halfferich *et al.*¹¹, who explained the variable interdiffusion coefficients on the basis of electro-potential gradient along the diffusion path.

The plot of Bt vs t at three different temperatures are straight-lines passing through the origin, indicating that the rate-determining step is diffusion through the particle. The B values calculated from these plots (Table 1) reveal that the diffusion coefficient for the present systems of exchange sorption increases with increase in temperature. This is in conformity with the earlier observations of temperature effect on exchange diffusion coefficient¹², and may be attributed to the increase in ionic mobility with temperature.

Fig. 1 indicates that the sorption of Fe^{3+} is greatly affected by changing dielectric constant of the medium. It is seen that the values of D_i are higher for exchange in pure aqueous medium as compared to the values obtained in presence of increasing proportions of isopropanol. Thus,

the presence of isopropanol has a retarding effect on the exchange rate that accounts for the lower value of D_i ¹³.

It is found (Table 1) that the energy of activation of the exchanging cation in pure aqueous solution is usually low compared to those obtained in presence of increasing proportions of isopropanol. This may be due to the low swelling of the resin particles in presence of organic solvent¹⁴.

The entropies of activation have been found to be negative for all the sorption systems studied. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger has been taken as indicative of a comparatively higher degree of mobility and the lack of an orientational effect which the ingoing ion influences upon its water-environment¹⁵.

Experimental

Ferric chloride, hydrochloric acid, EDTA disodium salt, salicylic acid and *p*-chloroaniline were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for preparing solutions.

Treatment of the ion exchanger : Lewatit CNO CP 3050 cation exchanger of ionic group COOH (H^+ -form) [exchange capacity 4 meq/g dry resin, moisture content 30–35 wt.%, granular phenolic matrix resins (Bayer)] was treated with ~ 1.0 M HCl for 24 h with occasional shaking and intermittent changing of the acid. The product was washed with demineralized water, dried at 40° , sieved (ASTM-E, 11-61) into two desired fractions (0.2 and 0.1 mm) and then placed in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Kinetic measurements : Rates of exchange were determined by limited batch technique⁸. Ferric chloride solution (100 ml) in water-0.005 M HCl with appropriate percentage of isopropanol at constant concentration of 0.01 M was shaken in a stoppered conical flask in a thermostat until the desired temperature was reached. Weighed amount of the exchanger (1 g) in H^+ -form was added to it and the flask was thoroughly shaken. After appropriate time intervals aliquots (1 ml each) were removed from the external solution phase and titrated with 0.01 M EDTA solution using salicylic acid *p*-chloroaniline as indicators¹⁶.

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